

**Synthesis of some New Schiff Bases from
8-Methoxycoumarin-3-carboxy(*o*-amino)-
anilide as Possible Antibacterial Agents**

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SOME Schiff bases exhibit various biological activities¹. In continuation of our earlier work on 8-methoxycoumarin, we report herein synthesis of some new Schiff bases by condensing 8-methoxycoumarin-3-carboxy(*o*-amino)anilide² with various substituted aromatic and heterocyclic aldehydes.

The structures of the compounds (Table 1) were assigned on the basis of their elemental analyses, ir, pmr and mass spectral data.

Experimental

All m ps. are uncorrected. The ^1H nmr spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard and the ir spectra (KBr) on a shimadzu 408 spectrophotometer. The homogeneity and purity of compounds were tested through tlc.

8-Methoxycoumarin-3-carboxy-o-(N-benzylidene)-anilide (2): A mixture of 8-methoxycoumarin-3-carboxy(o-amino)anilide (0.620 g, 0.002 mol) in ethanol (20 ml), benzaldehyde (0.212 g, 0.002 mol) and glacial acetic acid (2 drops) was refluxed for 2 h on a water-bath. The solid separated was filtered hot and crystallised from benzene as shining yellow crystals (70%), m.p. 255°.

Similarly, all other compounds (Table 1) were prepared and crystallised from proper solvent.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2*

Comp. no.	R	M.p.** °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
2a	Phenyl	255	70	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$
b	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	280	65	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2$
c	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	278	60	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2$
d	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	262	80	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2$
e	<i>m</i> -Methoxyphenyl	215	75	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2$
f	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	246	65	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_6\text{N}_2$
g	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	258	70	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_6\text{N}_3$
h	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	278	80	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_6\text{N}_3$
i	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	286	70	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_6\text{N}_3$
j	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	260	64	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$
k	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	253	70	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$
l	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	282	55	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$
m	5-Br,2-OH-phenyl	282	72	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{Br}$
n	5-Br,2-OH,3-OCH ₃ -phenyl	235	90	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_6\text{N}_2\text{Br}$
o	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	277	65	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$
p	β -Naphthyl	250	65	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$
q	β -OH- α -Naphthyl	241	70	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2$
r	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	258	65	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2$
s	4,5-Methylene-dioxyphenyl	272	75	$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6\text{N}_2$
t	Furfuryl	264	80	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2$

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

** All compounds were crystallised from benzene, except 2b from 1,4-dioxane.

Results and Discussion

The ir spectra of compounds 2a–t exhibited bands at 3 250–3 200m (NH), 1 720s (C=O of coumarin), 1 600 (aromatic C=C ring), 1 670–1 650 (amide-I), 1 560–1 540 (amide-II), 1 620–1 610 (C=N), 1 390–1 155 (C=N) and 1 100s cm^{-1} (C–O–C). The ir spectra of 1 showed characteristic bands at 3 450 and 3 350 cm^{-1} due to NH₂ and CO-NH groups, and the 3 450 cm^{-1} band disappeared in 2a–t. The pmr (90 MHz) spectra of 2d revealed the following signals: (CF₃COOH) 3.85 (6H, s, 2×OCH₃), 7.1–7.95 (m, br, aromatic and methine protons), 8.65 (1H, s, br, CONH) and 9.1 (1H, s, 4-H). The molecular ion at m/z 398, the base peak at m/z 195 (100%) and the other fragmentation peak at m/z 203 (50%) in mass spectrum of 2a are in agreement with the proposed structure 2.

Antibacterial activity: Some selected compounds 2a, 2f, 2g, 2i, 2j, 2k–m, 2p and 2r were screened for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method³ using *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *S. albus* and *S. typhosa* as test

strains at 100, 250, 500 and 1000 ppm concentration in DMF. Chloromycetin was used as a standard drug for comparison. The compounds did not show any antibacterial activity.

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